

Toward Flexible Neural Implant with Edge AI for Reversing Type 2 Diabetes

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Abstract—Type 2 Diabetes (T2D) affects over 11% of the U.S. population, with limited success from current therapies. Surgical interventions that alter stomach neural anatomy have demonstrated diabetes reversal, but underlying mechanisms remain unclear. We propose a diabetes wireless implant to record and stimulate vagus nerve activity, enabling real-time study of stomach–brain–pancreas signaling. The system integrates flexible Application Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) design, low-power edge computing, and semi-analog artificial intelligence/machine learning (AI/ML) for adaptive neuromodulation.

Clinical Relevance—This work aims to establish the feasibility of neural interface technologies for exploring novel diabetes treatments.

Index Terms—diabetes, ASIC implant, neural recordings, neuromodulation, AI.

I. INTRODUCTION

T2D is a major healthcare challenge, with 28.5% of U.S. adults in prediabetes and millions undiagnosed. Existing management strategies (lifestyle modification, medication, and surgical intervention) have shown only partial success [1]. Clinical observations suggest a neural basis for T2D reversal following gastric surgeries. However, limited understanding of vagus nerve signaling hampers the development of targeted neuromodulation therapies [2]. This research proposes an implantable system to investigate diabetes development and reversal from a neural perspective.

II. METHODS

The proposed flexible diabetes wireless implant with wearable pair is designed to operate reliably in the dynamic environment over the stomach while recording and stimulating vagus nerve signals [3]. The approach combines three components: (1) a flexible ASIC implant capable of withstanding mechanical and chemical stress while maintaining high-fidelity nerve interfacing; (2) low-power edge computing implemented directly on the ASIC, with semi-analog data processing to minimize wireless communication; and (3) novel signal processing and AI/ML algorithms optimized for constrained implant hardware (edge AI), enabling real-time adaptation, learning and neuromodulation. These elements enable a closed-loop

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Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed diabetes wireless implant-wearable.

platform for studying the neural mechanisms underlying T2D (see Fig. 1).

III. RESULTS AND EXPECTED OUTCOME

Our prior work show medical implant design with neural signal recording and stimulation capability [4]. This project is expected to demonstrate the feasibility of long-term functional implants for vagus nerve interfacing, while also establishing energy-efficient AI methods for adaptive neuromodulation under strict power and size constraints. Validation in small animals will be conducted to correlate vagus nerve activity with diabetes progression and reversal. The research will provide new insights into how vagus nerve signaling correlates with diabetes states, offering a foundation for the development of next-generation therapeutic implants that target metabolic disorders and potentially enable diabetes reversal.

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